

Varieties of 135-140 d duration represent group B. HBC-30,40,45,46, 85,98 and 136; Mohabawali, Kanwali, Chanderbani 1 and 11, Niranjapur, and Ramgarh (named after the villages of Dehra-Dun Valley) are phenotypically similar to Basmati 370 whereas Hansraj and N-10B resemble Type-3. Among these cultures, only Basmati 370 and Type-3 have been officially released for

cultivation and seed production.

Major differences in groups A and B (see table) appear to be in growth duration, milled rice length, length-to-breadth ratio, head rice recovery, and alkali spreading value. Difference in head rice recovery could possibly be due to postharvest handling and mechanical factors, but the lower mean value

(38.14%) in group A as compared to group B (47.24%) suggests higher vulnerability of longer grains to breakage.

Farmers grow Basmati 370, Type-3, and Karnal local under different names, warranting study of key diagnostic characteristics to establish their identities.□

Disease resistance

Varietal ranking of blast (BI) severity in Korean farmers' fields

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Varietal reactions to rice BI in farmers' fields and their relative ranking help determine resistance level, virulence frequency, disease pressure, and their interactions. Such rankings can guide cultural management.

To develop a varietal ranking in Korea, we used an indirect method without taking a comprehensive disease survey. We compared 56 varieties released in Korea: 26 of Tongil type (Korean indica) and 30 of japonica type. Most of the 51 varieties released before 1984 were grown in a considerable area. Cultivation area and duration of varieties vary widely, often highly influenced by BI. Criteria for comparisons were the relative degree of maximum leaf or panicle BI incidence and severity, yield losses due to BI, and chemical requirement. Varieties were classified into 9 groups (Table 1), and common features of five odd-numbered ranking groups were described (Table 2). Ranking groups 2,4, 6, and 8 reflect severity levels between those of the odd-numbered groups described. To minimize subjectivity, five evaluators rated each variety several times until they unanimously agreed.

Varieties scored 1 or 2, such as Taebaeg and Cheongcheong, were

Table 1. Relative ranking of Korean varieties based on BI severity in farmers' field. Korea, 1988.

Rank	Tongil type	Japonica type
1	<u>Taebaeg</u> (79), Chupung (79)	
2		
3	Cheongcheong (79), <u>Samgang</u> (182)	
4	Palgwang (78), Milyang 42 (78) Milyang 30 (77)	
5	Gaya (82), <u>Weonpung</u> (83), <u>Baegyung</u> (82), <u>Shinwang</u> (82)	Shinseonhd (82), <u>Seomjin</u> (82), Nonglim Na 1 (67)
6	<u>Seogwang</u> (79), <u>Hangangchal</u> (79)	Nongbaeg (69), <u>Odae</u> (82), Seolag (79), <u>Sobaeg</u> (82), Boggwang (81), Dobong (79), Sangpung (81), Kwanak (79), Yeongdeog (85), <u>Dongiin</u> (81), Daechong (84), <u>Bonggwang</u> (74)
7	Baegunchal (79), Pungsan (81), <u>Nampung</u> (81)	<u>Chiag</u> (81), Gwangmyeong (84), Namyang (83)
8	Saetbeol (77), Geumgang (77)	<u>Daechang</u> (81), Yeomyeong (77), Jinheung (62), Palgeum (67). <u>Chugwang</u> (81)
9	Milyang 23 (76), Sujeong (81), <u>Yeongpung</u> (82), Nopung (77), Tongil (71), Yushin (75), Hwanggeum (76), <u>Chilseong</u> (84)	<u>Seonam</u> (82), <u>Giho</u> (83), Cheonma (84), Jiniu (79), <u>Nagdong</u> (75), Samnam (81), <u>Chucheone</u> (70)

^aTotal planting area of underlined varieties is more than 5,000 ha for Tongil type, and more than 10,000 ha for japonica type as of 1986. Figures in parentheses indicate year the variety was released.

planted in more than 10,000 ha each until 1984, but their levels of quantitative (partial or field) resistance are not known because compatible isolates were either absent or extremely low in frequency. Variety Samgang was cultivated in more than 130,000 ha from 1984 to 1987, yet no severe BI outbreak was observed. Several varieties scoring 4 or 5, such as Seomjin, Milyang 42, and Milyang 30, have high levels of quantitative resistance. They occasionally may require one or two chemical applications. Varieties that scored 6 frequently need four applications, two for leaf BI and two for

Table 2. Common features of Korean varieties in each ranking group of BI severity in farmers' fields. Korea, 1988.

Rank	Common features
1	Extremely low incidence and severity.
3	Low incidence with minor damage. Chemical application seldom necessary.
5	BI is common. Low to moderate severity, without severe yield loss. Three or fewer chemical applications sufficient.
7	Moderate to high incidence and severity. Four or five application needed.
9	Severe BI and significant yield loss. Extensive chemical application required, with control less than anticipated.

panicle BL. Varieties scored higher than 6 are vulnerable to BL and damage could be high. Cultivation of many cultivars in rank 9 was discontinued because of severe outbreak of BL. Yet several late-

maturing varieties with good grain quality favored by Koreans are widely grown in the southern plain of Korea with intensive applications of chemicals for BL control. On these varieties, panicle

BL is less severe than leaf BL.

The ranking can be applied to other varieties when no historical quantitative disease data are available. □

Varietal reaction to tungro (RTV) with change in leafhopper "virulence"

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Green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* populations were periodically collected at Koronadal, South Cotabato; Maligaya, Nueva Ecija; and Los Baños (IRRI Experimental Farm), Laguna, in the Philippines in 1986-88 and reared on TN1 plants in cages in an insect-proof greenhouse. First or second generation adults that had fed on RTV-infected plants were allowed to feed 1 d on test seedlings. GLH feeding behavior was monitored by the color reaction of honeydew excreted by GLH on bromocresol-treated filter paper disks: blue color (basic reaction) indicates phloem feeding and brown or orange color (acidic reaction) indicates xylem feeding. At 3 wk after the feeding, seedlings were indexed by latex serology for the presence of rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses.

GLH populations collected thrice at Koronadal had similar transmission efficiency and feeding behavior on each test cultivar. GLH populations collected thrice at Maligaya were also similar. All these populations transmitted RTBV and RTSV together (RTBV + RTSV) at high efficiency and fed mainly from both phloem and xylem on IR54.

Six populations collected at Los Baños varied in their transmission efficiencies and feeding behavior, especially on IR54. Populations collected prior to Apr 1987 transmitted mostly RTBV alone and fed mainly from xylem on IR54. Populations collected after Aug 1987 efficiently transmitted RTBV + RTSV, and fed predominantly from both phloem and

Area of acidic and basic honeydew spots (a), percentage of area of basic honeydew spots (b) excreted by 6 GLH collections from IRRI farm, Los Baños, Philippines, Aug 1986-Jan 1988, during a 22-h inoculation feeding, and transmission of RTBV and RTSV to 6 rice cultivars (c). IRRI, 1988.

RTBV and RTSV incidence^a in 14 rice cultivars in demonstration plots at IRRI, 1986 and 1988 DS.^b

Cultivar	1986 dry season			1988 dry season				
	Plants tested (no.)	Plants (%) with		Plants tested (no.)	Plants (%) with			
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
IR8	—	—	—	—	36	56	14	19
IR22	36	87	11	2	—	—	—	—
IR26	36	0	59	0	36	0	31	0
IR30	36	0	41	0	36	0	25	0
IR36	36	67	7	15	36	11	0	75
IR42	36	70	12	10	36	61	0	36
IR54	36	1	3	19	56	71	11	16
IR58	36	0	0	9	36	3	0	33
IR64	50 ^c	0	6	12	70	66	4	23
Gam Pai 30-12-15	90 ^d	0	1	9	34	80	15	0
Sigadis	—	50	22	7	34	38	9	24
Peta	90 ^d	2	12	7	36	78	8	6
TN1	36	83	13	2	—	—	—	—

^aPlants were indexed by latex serology. ^bDashes indicate not tested. ^cTested in 1985 WS. ^dTested in 1985 DS.

xylem on IR54 and IR64 (see figure). Additional measurements Jan-Feb 1988 confirmed this. The shift in feeding

behavior on IR54 and IR64 of the Los Baños population from predominant xylem feeding to phloem and xylem